

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object;

REPRESENTASI TERAPI KOGNITIF PERILAKU (COGNITIVE BEHAVIOURAL THERAPY) DALAM DUNIA MIMPI SERIAL ANIMASI WONDER EGG PRIORITY

Background and Analysis

Abstrak:

Kajian ini bertujuan untuk mengidentifikasi representasi permasalahan kesehatan mental dan psikoterapi dalam penokohan maupun alur cerita serial animasi Wonder Egg Priority. Dalam penelitian ini unsur-unsur dalam cerita yang menggambarkan kondisi mental tokoh dan proses psikoterapi diidentifikasi dan ditarik kesimpulan melalui validasi teoritis. Subjek yang diteliti adalah serial animasi Wonder Egg Priority dan objek yang diteliti adalah kondisi mental tokoh utama dan petualangan yang mereka tempuh menghadapi permasalahan tersebut.

Serial animasi Wonder Egg Priority mampu memberikan representasi masalah mental yang lazim dialami oleh remaja seusia para tokoh utama. Selain itu penggambaran upaya mengatasi masalah tersebut tergambar dengan baik pada simulasi dunia mimpi yang menjadi premis utama dalam serial animasi tersebut.

Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Qustions:

- 1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,
Ya, ada data yang dilakukan dalam jurnal ini dengan menganalisis dan memperoleh informasi

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- 2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,
Ya, data atau informasi tersebut diperoleh melalui metode ilmiah, seperti Di beberapa bagian makalah penelitian, kontennya berasal dari sumber sekunder dari situs web online, dan jurnal, bagian kualitatif dari penelitian dilakukan dengan mengamati beberapa faktor untuk menemukan mengungkap makna tersembunyi dari film itu sendiri berdasarkan hasil penelitian kualitatif.
- 3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),
Ya, Jurnal Ini Diidentifikasi melalui penelitian sebelumnya, makalah ini memenuhi persyaratan:
orisinalitas karena merupakan ide dan pemikiran saya sendiri.
- 4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,
Makalah ini tidak memberikan teoretis dan bagi perkembangan ilmu pengetahuan.
- 5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,
Isu-isu yang terjadi tidak mengandung konflik karena pelajaran yang diambil atau diteliti adalah pesan moral yang bisa diamalkan
- 6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and
Rumusan masalah terdapat dalam setiap penelitian yang diharapkan bagi pembaca masyarakat untuk memahami jurnal yang sedang kita diskusikan dan yang di cermati si pembaca tersebut.
- 7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.
Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk menambah wawasan si pembaca tersebut.
- 8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

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Terjadi pada saat pembunuhan yang berada dalam sadar mimpi.

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

Untuk membangun kepercayaan diri kita, kita harus mengidentifikasi apa

masalahnya ada di dalam diri kita sendiri. Setelah kita tahu apa masalahnya dengan kita, maka kita harus mencoba

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